

Developing a SAM Multiplier Analysis for the Zambian economy: Energy Investments

Working Paper

Bernard Tembo and Steve Pye

March 2024

1. Introduction	3
2. The Social Accounting Matrix and associated Multiplier Analysis	4
2.1 The Social Accounting Matrix (SAM)	4
2.2 An overview of multiplier analysis approaches	7
3. Approach: The use of a Zambian SAM to develop a multiplier analysis	9
3.1 Zambian 2019 SAM and extension	9
3.2 Zambian Multiplier Model	10
3.3 Energy investments from scenario modelling	11
4. Results: Multiplier analysis based on prospective Zambian energy sector investments	12
4.1 Analysing the extended 2019 SAM	12
4.2 The macroeconomic implications of energy investments	16
5. Concluding Remarks	17
References	19
Annexes	21

1. Introduction

Zambia has the ambition to develop its economy and meet a range of development objectives to attain middle income status, as put forward in its Vision 2030 document (GRZ, 2006). In doing so, the energy sector will play a key role as an enabler of growth, and will need to expand significantly. This will need to be done whilst minimising emissions, ensuring security of supply, and promoting energy access to all sections of society.

The country's development priorities (specifically energy sector focused) and implementation strategies necessary for leading Zambia towards this vision (Vision 2030) are set out in various policies, strategies and successive National Development Plans, most recently the eighth (8NDP). Taking into account the sectors identified as crucial to Zambia's economic development, the main policies and programs have been assessed and are summarised in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Key policies and document relevant to energy and socioeconomic development in Zambia

Policy/Strategy	Year	Focus
Vision 2030	2006	The document "articulates possible long-term alternative development policy scenarios at different points which would contribute to the attainment of the desirable social economic indicators by the year 2030."
Eighth National Development Plan (8NDP)	2022	This is a "comprehensive document that was formulated through a highly consultative and participatory process, involving stakeholders across all sectors." It identifies energy as one of the key drivers of economic transformation and job creation, and emphasises the need to enhance security of energy supply and diversifying the supply of energy to clean and resilient technologies.
National Energy Policy	2019	An overarching energy sector document provides specific measures, development and implementation, frameworks and principles for the energy market. Overall, the policy seeks to promote diversification of energy sources and new investment in the sector, including scaling up access to energy services in rural areas.
Zambia National Policy on Climate Change	2016	"The Policy's main objective is to provide a framework for coordinating climate change programmes in order to ensure climate resilient and low carbon development pathways for sustainable development towards the attainment of Zambia's Vision 2030."

Recent work by Zambia Institute for Policy Analysis and Research (ZIPAR) and University College London (UCL) highlighted how clean investment in the energy sector could help meet longer term

development objectives, and help 'green' the recovery from the Covid pandemic (Nyambe-Mubanga et al., 2023). Two modelled scenarios were developed; the first, *centralised*, focused on 'policy approaches that reflect the government's stated interest in an export-led trade strategy, and for investment in large-scale infrastructure, leveraging public-private partnership investment.' The second, *decentralised*, focused on 'policy approaches that reflect the President's stated interest in decentralisation and devolution of various central government functions... that will be better managed at the local level with appreciation for local challenges.'

Both scenarios demonstrate that through sizable investments, future energy demand growth can be met whilst minimising emissions. This includes up to a 10 times expansion in electricity generation, largely through investment in renewable capacity. However, the Greening the Recovery (GtR) analysis did not provide insights on the broader economic implications of the resulting energy system build out. The purpose of this paper is to propose an approach for filling this gap, through the estimation of macroeconomic impacts of energy sector investments in Zambia. For this, we propose the use of a multiplier analysis using a Social Accounting Matrix (SAM). It is hoped that such an analysis can provide easy-to-derive estimates of broader economic impacts, to complement approaches focused on the energy sector more broadly.

This paper is structured as follows; section 2 describes the use of SAMs and associated multiplier analysis for providing estimates of the wider economic impacts of investment. Section 3 sets out the application of this approach in the Zambia context, including the development of an extended Zambian SAM to enable a focus on energy sector investments. It also introduces the modelling analysis of investment pathways for Zambia, which are then used in the analysis described in section 4. Section 5 sets out some concluding remarks on the insights, and outlines further research opportunities.

2. The Social Accounting Matrix and associated Multiplier Analysis

2.1 The Social Accounting Matrix (SAM)

We first describe what a Social Accounting Matrix (SAM) is before explaining how it is used to develop a multiplier analysis. By definition, a SAM is a comprehensive and economy-wide database recording data on transactions between economic agents in a certain economy during a certain period of time, typically a year. The SAM covers two main areas: it provides data for economic modelling (multi-sectoral linear models or the more complex Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) Models) and it provides a complete but intuitive snapshot of the current economy (Mainar-Causepe et al., 2018). Historically, the idea of a SAM can be traced to Stone (1947), whose pioneering work on social accounting includes most of the conventions which would later be followed by economic and statistical organisations. The idea was then formalised by Pyatt & Thorbecke (1976) who facilitated its use as a formal framework for economic analysis and planning.

At the core of a SAM is the economic concept of circular flow of income. The circular flow (see Figure 1 below) captures the generation of income by activities in producing commodities, the mapping of these income payments to factors of production of various kinds, the distribution of factor and non-factor income to households, and the subsequent spending of income by households on commodities. These patterns of payments are manifested in the structure of the SAM, and are also modelled analogously to the input structure of activities in an input-output model based only on inter-industry transactions.

Figure 1: Circular flow of income (Cooper and John, 2012)

Understanding the socioeconomic and employment outcomes of the response to climate change and related sustainable policy options is essential for policy makers. For instance, policy makers want to know the potential job outcomes in order to design strategies that can maximise job creation, minimise job losses and ensure a just transition for all in the process of restructuring to a clean and green economy. Tools such as a SAM therefore become essential in quantifying, qualifying and projecting the social and employment outcomes of climate-related policy alternatives. In particular, the SAM is well suited to analysing the impact on jobs and income distribution. The SAM makes it possible to analyse direct, indirect and induced job effects at the sector level. Because it is based on national accounts and data collected at the country level, it is transparent, accessible and relatively easy to build and use (ILO, 2017). With respect to the policy cycle, the SAM is useful for policy formulation and evaluation due to its socioeconomic coverage.

Table 2 (below) shows the structure of a basic SAM which is laid out as a square matrix in which each transaction or account has its own row and column. The payments are listed in columns, and receipts are recorded in rows. The sum of all expenditures by a given account must equal the total sum of receipts or income for the corresponding account.

Table 2: The Basic SAM structure

	Production (P)	Factors (F)	House Holds (HH)	Government (G)	Savings / Invest (S/I)	Rest of World (RoW)	Total
P	Intermediate Inputs		Private consumption	Gov. consumption	Investment	Export	Demand
F	Value added					Factor inc. from ROW	Factor income
HH		Factor inc. to HH	Inter HH Transfers	Transfers to HH		Transfer to HH	HH income
G	Prod., sales, export, VAT	Factor inc. to G, factor taxes	Transfers to G, direct			Transfer to G	G income
S/I			HH savings	Gov. savings		Foreign	Savings

						savings	
Row	Imports	Factor inc. to ROW		Gov. transfers to ROW			Foreign exch. outflow
Total	Supply expend.	Factor expend	HH expend	Gov. expend.	Investment	Foreign exch. inflow	

Source: Adapted from Peterson (2003)

Typically, a SAM has six basic groups of accounts: activities and/or commodities, production (factors), (private) institutions – households and corporations/enterprises, government (public institutions), (combined) capital accounts, and accounts for the rest of the world (as shown in Table 2). The six components of the SAM can be summed up into three broad categories as presented by Breisinger et al., (2009).

The first category is that of “activities” and “commodities.” Activities are the entities that produce goods and services, and commodities are those goods and services produced by activities. Activities produce goods and services by combining the factors of production with intermediate inputs. This is shown in the activity column of the SAM, where activities pay for the wages, rents, and profits they generate during the production process (value-added). Essentially, this is a payment from activities to factors, and so the value-added entry in the SAM appears in the activity column and the factor row. Likewise, intermediate demand is a payment from activities to commodities and so adding together value-added and intermediate demand gives gross output. Commodities are either supplied domestically or imported. Indirect sales taxes and import tariffs are paid on these commodities and this means that the values in the commodity accounts are measured at market prices.

The second broad category is that of domestic institutions. It is worth noting that a SAM is different from an input–output matrix (or table) because it not only traces the income and expenditure flows of activities and commodities, but it also contains complete information on different institutional accounts, such as households and the government. Households are usually the ultimate owners of the factors of production, and so they receive the incomes earned by factors during the production process. They also receive transfer payments from the government, such as social security and pensions, and from the rest of the world (remittances received from family members working abroad). It then follows that households pay taxes directly to the government and purchase commodities. The remaining income is then saved (or dis-saved if expenditures exceed incomes). It is worth noting that information in household accounts is usually drawn from national accounts and household surveys from the country’s statistics bureau. The government receives transfer payments from the rest of the world (such as foreign grants and development assistance). This is added to all of the different tax incomes to determine total government revenues. These revenues are used by the government to pay for recurrent consumption spending and transfers to households. From the difference between total revenues and expenditures we then have a fiscal surplus (or deficit, if expenditures exceed revenues).

The third broad category is that of savings, investment and foreign accounts. According to the ex-post accounting identity, investment or gross capital formation, which includes changes in stocks or inventories, must equal total savings. The difference between total domestic savings and total investment demand is total capital inflows from abroad, or what is called the current account balance. This is also equal to the difference between foreign exchange receipts (exports and foreign transfers

received) and expenditures (imports and government transfers to foreigners). Information on the current account (or rest of the world) is drawn from the balance of payments, which is usually published by a country's central bank.

In a broad sense, the SAM is associated with exogenous demand-side shocks which refer to changes in export demand, government spending, or investment demand. Thus, the impacts of these shocks can have both direct and indirect effects. In this sense, direct effects are those pertaining to the sector that is directly affected by the shock. These indirect linkages can, in turn, be separated into production and consumption linkages. Adding up all direct and indirect linkages leads to a measure of the shock's multiplier effect, or how much a direct effect is amplified or multiplied by indirect linkage effects (Breisinger et al., 2009).

Production linkages which are determined by sectors' production technologies can be split into forward and backward linkages. Backward linkages are defined as the demands for additional inputs used by producers to supply additional goods or services whereas forward production linkages account for the increased supply of inputs to upstream industries. Stronger forward and backward linkages lead to larger multipliers. Also worth noting is that SAM multipliers capture the consumption linkages, which arise when an expansion of production generates additional incomes for factors and households, which are then used to purchase goods and services. As such, SAM multipliers tend to be larger than input-output multipliers because they capture both production and consumption/income linkages (Breisinger et al., 2009).

Principally, SAM multipliers measure the value of all production and consumption linkage effects. They capture direct and indirect effects in the first and all subsequent rounds of the circular income flow. Specifically, multipliers explain initial changes in exogenous demand (for example, increased agricultural export demand) into total production and income changes of endogenous accounts. The size of a multiplier depends on the structural characteristics of an economy. For instance, a key factor is the share of imported goods and services in households' consumption demand. If households consume domestically produced goods, then increasing household incomes will benefit domestic producers and the circular flow of income will lead to further rounds of indirect linkage effects.

Yet, if households demand imported goods, then it is foreign producers who benefit and the indirect linkage effects will be smaller. Therefore, import demand is a leakage from the circular flow of income. In the same way, when the government taxes factor incomes, it limits how much of the returns to production are earned to households, and so reduces consumption linkages. Eventually, these kinds of leakages make the round-by-round effects slow down more quickly and reduce the total multiplier effect (Breisinger et al., 2009).

2.2 An overview of multiplier analysis approaches

There are two types of multipliers that can be developed, namely an unconstrained multiplier and a constrained multiplier. The difference between the two lies in the assumptions made. Under the unconstrained multiplier, it is assumed that prices are fixed and that any changes in demand will lead to changes in physical output rather than prices. This in turn requires an additional assumption that the economy's factor resources are unlimited or unconstrained, so that any increase in demand can be matched by an increase in supply. The model also assumes that all structural relationships between sectors and households in the economy are unaffected by exogenous changes in demand. Using matrix algebra, a multiplier is then developed which shows that when exogenous demand

increases, then after taking all rounds of direct and indirect linkage effects into account, we end up with a final increase in total demand.

The constrained multiplier drops the assumption that sectors' supply responses are unconstrained by fixing the level of output in certain sectors. This requires some adjustments to the multiplier formula to derive a constrained multiplier model. The equation for the constrained multiplier represents a condition where an exogenous increase in demand for the unconstrained sectors leads to a final increase in total demand for these sectors, including all of the forward and backward linkages. However, for the sectors with constrained supply, it is the net exports that decline while imports increase to replace the shortfall in domestic production. Because exports are now included inside exogenous demand, the equations solve for the impact of a change in demand on net exports, rather than the other way around (Breisinger et al., 2009).

Multiplier analysis can provide a useful simplified assessment, notably in countries where dynamic economy-wide models, such as Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) models, are not available. For such models, fairly advanced analytical skills and time are required to undertake economy-wide investigations. Further, many people may not easily understand and interpret economy-wide models.

There are many examples of multiplier analyses that have focused on a developing country context and explored the impact of investment in renewable energy, as is being focused on in this paper. Milani et al. (2020) used such an analysis to assess the impact of a 300 MW solar thermal programme in Brazil on jobs, incomes and economic output. Vasconcellos and Caiado Couto (2021) estimated the economic impacts of investment in wind generation in North East Brazil. Garrett-Peltier (2017) used input-output analysis to determine the relative job creation associated with investment in renewables versus fossil fuels, finding that investment in renewables leads to much larger employment multipliers. For a multiplier analysis, either the focus is on a specific project investment or investment profiles can be generated by other modelling - and fed into the SAM. A useful example of this approach is documented for Tunisia, in Howells et al. (2021). This study, as developed in sections 3.1 and 3.2, derives multipliers from a SAM multiplier model and uses investments from a country-level OSeMOSYS model to assess economic impacts, notably on GDP and household income.

While SAM multipliers provide detailed analysis about the linkages, income distribution etc., there are some important limitations. Firstly, in many cases certain accounts such as factors and households might be too aggregated to understand any relationships. For example, economy-wide models using the Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP), have historically assumed one type of household for the country and region. However, households differ by urban or rural setup. In addition, households differ by income levels and sources of income. Some households depend on wages and self-employment while others subsist on transfers and remittances. As such, their use of one household type in economy wide models can be misleading (Sigwele, 2007).

Secondly, data are required from national accounts, household and income surveys as well as farm or agricultural surveys. In many countries these data may not be available at the same time in order for one to conduct a SAM-based analysis. Finally, such analyses are by their nature static, meaning that any policy shocks that flow through the SAM do not result in price feedbacks and a revised SAM; in other words, the structure of the economy is not changed in the subsequent period that would be needed to allow for a recursive analysis.

3. Approach: The use of a Zambian SAM to develop a multiplier analysis

3.1 Zambian 2019 SAM and extension

Zambia's 2019 SAM used in this analysis was developed by the International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI), with a base year of 2019 (Pauw et al., 2021). The 2019 base year SAM was preferred to the 2021 SAM, developed soon after (Pauw et al., 2022), because 2019 is arguably a better representation of Zambia's economy as it was before the COVID-19 pandemic. A comparative analysis of these SAMs can be found in Annex 3. The SAM has three macroeconomic accounts: government balance, current account, and savings-investment macroeconomic accounts. It is a more disaggregated SAM compared to Zambia's 2007 (Zali et al., 2013) and 2010 (ZamStats, 2022) SAMs, and has more disaggregated agricultural sector activities (capturing major all crops and livestock) and households by region (rural-urban split). In total, it has 42 economic activities, a total of 10 household types and a total of three labour types. However, this SAM only has one electricity activity and commodity type, and given the focus of our analysis on energy investment, it was important to make some extensions to this SAM.

With the base 2019 SAM already in place, the starting point of the extension was to split three sectors (mine, chem and elec) into 'mining' (mine), 'chemicals and petroleum' (chem), and 'electricity, gas and steam' (elec) activity and commodity sectors - into more detail to give a total of sixteen sectors. The correspondence between the old and new sectors are shown in Table 3. The intention was to remain entirely consistent with the original IFPRI SAM and split the three sectors using other data; therefore, it should be to simply aggregate the new sectors, created and detailed in this document, together to create the original SAM.

The main other data sources used to undertake the disaggregation are electricity generation statistics from Zesco Limited Power (ZESCO, 2022) and the Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP 10) database (Aguar et al. 2019). The former provided the electricity generation by technology in 2019 for Zambia, the base year of the IFPRI SAM. The latter, the GTAP-Power database, provided a SAM for Zambia for 2014 which has greater detail on the sectors of interest here. Therefore, it was possible to use the GTAP database to inform the cost structure in our disaggregation. For the sake of simplicity, we do not disaggregate between base load and peak electricity generating technologies and therefore when using GTAP-Power data these are aggregated together and considered as one (e.g., in GTAP-Power there are both baseload and peak electricity generation from gas and oil, these are combined for our database).

Details of this disaggregation activity can be found in Annex 2 of this paper.

Table 3: Mapping of old sectors to new sectors

IFPRI original sector	Description	New sectors	Description
mine	Mining	coal	Mining of coal
		oil	Oil extraction
		gas	Extraction of gas
		miner	All other mining including metals, minerals etc.
chem	Chemicals and	petrol	Petroleum, coal products

	petroleum	chem	Chemical products
elec	Electricity, gas and water	edist	Electricity transmission and distribution
		enucl	Electricity from nuclear energy
		ecoal	Electricity from coal power
		ewind	Electricity from wind power
		eothe	Electricity from other power sources
		egas	Electricity from gas
		ehydro	Electricity from hydro power
		eoil	Electricity from oil
		esolar	Electricity from solar power

3.2 Zambian Multiplier Model

The Zambian multiplier model is based on the framework provided in IFPRI's Social Accounting Matrices and Multiplier Analysis: An Introduction with Exercises (Breisinger et al., 2009), which is itself based on the Leontief model (see Miller and Blair (2009) for a detailed discourse on the Leontief model).

Given that a SAM contains activities among various economic agents of a given economy, below is a summary derivation of the SAM multiplier model for a two-sector economy:

Total demand Z is expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} Z_1 &= a_{11}X_1 + a_{12}X_2 + c_1Y + E_1 \\ Z_2 &= a_{21}X_1 + a_{22}X_2 + c_2Y + E_2 \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eqn (1)}$$

Where:

a_{11} and a_{21} are commodities in the first and second rows of the matrix respectively,
 a_{12} and a_{22} are commodities in the first and second columns of the matrix respectively,
 $X_i = b_i * Z_i$ is domestic production,
 $Y = v_i * X_i$ is household income, and
 E_i is exogenous demand.

After substituting and separating endogenous variables from exogenous variables, equation (1) can be rewritten in matrix form as

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 - a_{11}b_1 - c_1v_1b_1 & -a_{12}b_2 - c_1v_2b_2 \\ -a_{21}b_1 - c_2v_1b_1 & 1 - a_{22}b_2 - c_2v_2b_2 \end{pmatrix} * \begin{pmatrix} Z_1 \\ Z_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} E_1 \\ E_2 \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{Eqn (2)}$$

After rearranging equation (2), we get an unconstrained multiplier equation

$$Z = (I - M)^{-1} * E \quad \text{Eqn (3)}$$

Where:

Z is the total demand vector,

$(I - M)^{-1}$ is the multiplier matrix (this takes into account both the direct and indirect multiplier effects), and

E is the exogenous demand vector.

Under the constrained model, sectors that can change their production levels are distinguished from those that cannot. For the sectors that cannot change their production levels, there will be endogenous imports substitution. Thus, under the constrained model, equation (3) is rewritten as

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 - a_{11}b_1 - c_1v_1b_1 & 0 \\ -a_{21}b_1 - c_2v_1b_1 & -1 \end{pmatrix} * \begin{pmatrix} Z_1 \\ E_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & a_{12}b_2 + c_1v_2b_2 \\ 0 & -1 + a_{22}b_2 + c_2v_2b_2 \end{pmatrix} * \begin{pmatrix} E_1 \\ Z_2 \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{Eqn (4)}$$

After substituting for $(I - M^*)$ and B , we get a constrained multiplier equation

$$\begin{pmatrix} Z_1 \\ E_2 \end{pmatrix} = (I - M^*)^{-1} * B * \begin{pmatrix} E_1 \\ Z_2 \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{Eqn (5)}$$

Where:

$(I - M^*)^{-1}$ is the adjusted multiplier matrix (this takes into account both the forward and backward linkages), and

B is a term which acts as one of constraining factors,

Due to limited supply from the constrained sectors, it implies that as demand grows in unconstrained sectors, net exports in the constrained sectors reduce. This reduction acts as a limiting factor to the overall economic growth of an economy.

3.3 Energy investments from scenario modelling

The purpose of constructing the SAM is to assess the impact of energy investments on the wider economy. Such investments are derived from scenario modelling undertaken as part of the Greening the Recovery project, as described in Nyambe-Mubanga et al. (2023). Two scenarios, *centralised* and *decentralised*, provide the investment profiles that are used as input into the multiplier analysis. For the power sector, *centralised* represents significant investment in grid-scale generation plants, with a focus on wind and solar. Post-2030, a five-fold increase in the total electricity production is observed, due to strong demand growth, particularly from the mining sector. *Decentralised* sees lower demand levels due to lower mobility demands, a more diverse mix of cooking fuels, more uptake of efficiency measures, and a smaller mining sector.

The investments are estimated using the OSeMOSYS-Zambia whole energy system model. OSeMOSYS is a modelling platform for exploring different energy system futures required to meet specified energy service demands (Howells et al., 2011). As shown here, it can provide insights under different scenarios as to the level of energy supply needed, the types of technologies needed, the investment requirements of those future systems, plus how this impacts CO₂ emissions. It uses a linear optimisation approach to determine least cost pathways, considering policy objectives and other factors, such as resource and technology availability. Full details on modelling assumptions can be found in Nyambe-Mubanga et al. (2023).

Table 4 gives the yearly averages of capital investment (in USD millions, 2019 basis) for these investment profiles broken down by scenarios and generation technology type. The considered time horizon is 2020 to 2050.

Table 4: Average yearly capital investment (in USD million) in the energy sector (Source: Nyambe-Mubanga et al., 2023)

	2020-2050			2020-2030			2031-2040			2041-2050		
	<i>Ref</i>	<i>Centr</i>	<i>Decentr</i>									
Gas	116.6	246.2	6.2	9.6	0	8.73	4.7	177.8	0	346.2	585.5	9.6
Oil	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Coal	0	42.7	24.2	0	0	68.2	0	132.5	0	0	0	0
Biomass	0	204.7	118.0	0	0	102.6	0	325.9	107.8	0	308.7	145.0
Solar	264.2	585.1	485.2	18.3	0	100.5	212.1	597	366.6	586.6	1,216.9	1,026.9
Wind	173.1	515.5	433.7	0	0	115.4	284.5	675.1	633.3	252.0	922.87	584.1
Hydro	344.6	344.6	112.7	579.7	923.8	317.3	430.3	51.8	0	0.3	0.3	0.3
Imports & Infr.	78.3	177.1	91.8	45.2	76.6	55.5	71.8	162.8	99.5	121.1	301.8	124.1

4. Results: Multiplier analysis based on prospective Zambian energy sector investments

This section focuses on the general multiplier effects across the economy (both for unconstrained and constrained models), and the specific multiplier effects based on the investment in different technologies, in both the centralised and decentralised scenarios relative to the reference case. On specific multiplier effects, the analysis assesses the impacts of investments in energy projects on Zambia's economy, the investments of which are highlighted in Table 4 above. In both analyses, the focus is on shock effects on GDP, household income and economic output.

4.1 Analysing the extended 2019 SAM

For ease of result presentation and in order to emphasise the energy sector investment, selected commodities in the extended 2019 SAM (described in Section 3 above) were aggregated. See Table A1 in the Annex for how this aggregation was mapped.

Table 5 presents the multiplier effects on GDP, output and income due to a shock (increase) of K1 billion in final demand of each commodity, in an unconstrained model (see Equation (3) above). As an example, a one-unit shock (i.e., one billion Kwacha) in electricity produced from natural gas will result in K1.18 billion in GDP. Further, this unit increase in demand would also result in K2.31 billion total output and K0.81 billion household income. This effect includes the direct effect on electricity from natural gas and the indirect effects on the rest of the sectors.

From Table 5, it can be seen that while increased demand in electricity produced from natural gas has the largest impact on GDP, the commodities with the largest effect on output and income are electricity produced from oil (K2.37 billion) and livestock (K0.88 billion) respectively. This suggests

that in the quest to grow an economy, careful consideration should be given to the chosen macroeconomic indicator to monitor, as growth in GDP does not always imply an increase in household income, and vice-versa.

Table 5: GDP, Output and Income Effects from K 1 billion in final demand of each commodity (Units: K billion)

Commodity	GDP	Output	Income
Elect. Gen. - Gas	1.178	2.306	0.812
Livestock	1.167	2.271	0.883
Elect. Distr.	1.135	1.757	0.817
Crop	1.131	1.89	0.87
Elect. Gen. - Hydro	1.127	1.624	0.735
Elect. Gen. - Other	1.121	2.305	0.783
Construction	1.111	2.25	0.855
Forestry	1.104	2.181	0.825
Elect. Gen. - Wind	1.101	1.977	0.745
Water	1.096	2.146	0.784
Elect. Gen. - Coal	1.073	1.956	0.719
Elect. Gen. - Solar	1.069	1.946	0.71
Services	1.064	1.747	0.741
Fisheries	1.028	1.899	0.739
Elect. Gen. - Oil	0.973	2.366	0.724
Mining	0.918	1.691	0.606
Manufacturing	0.707	1.244	0.492
Petroleum	0.395	0.743	0.27
Chemicals	0.392	0.773	0.272

Tables 6 and 7 below show the effects that a unit demand positive shock (of K1 billion) has on household income and labour respectively. For income, a K1 billion shock in final demand of crop commodities results in K0.39 billion in urban household type 5 and K0.04 billion in rural household type 1.¹ Overall, the urban household types 1 and 2 seem to be the least impacted by all commodity demand shocks, highlighting the distributional effects and the tendency for benefits to be higher for higher income households.

Table 6: Disaggregated Household Income Effects (Units: K billion)

Commodity	GDP	hhd-r1	hhd-r2	hhd-r3	hhd-r4	hhd-r5	hhd-u1	hhd-u2	hhd-u3	hhd-u4	hhd-u5
Elect. Gen. - Gas	1.178	0.012	0.023	0.032	0.037	0.042	0.002	0.007	0.032	0.112	0.514

¹ Household types 1 to 5 represent quintiles of household expenditure. The higher the number the higher the quintile. For instance, Type 1 is 20% quintile. Further, r and u in Table 6 represent rural and urban respectively.

Livestock	1.167	0.024	0.043	0.054	0.052	0.048	0.003	0.01	0.04	0.115	0.493
Elect. Distr.	1.135	0.011	0.021	0.03	0.037	0.046	0.002	0.007	0.03	0.109	0.523
Crop	1.131	0.038	0.074	0.094	0.081	0.057	0.002	0.009	0.03	0.091	0.394
Elect. Gen. - Hydro	1.127	0.01	0.019	0.026	0.031	0.035	0.002	0.006	0.028	0.103	0.476
Elect. Gen. - Other	1.121	0.012	0.023	0.031	0.036	0.041	0.002	0.007	0.031	0.107	0.493
Construction	1.111	0.018	0.032	0.042	0.045	0.049	0.003	0.009	0.037	0.113	0.509
Forestry	1.104	0.024	0.042	0.051	0.047	0.039	0.004	0.011	0.044	0.113	0.449
Elect. Gen. - Wind	1.101	0.011	0.021	0.028	0.033	0.037	0.002	0.007	0.029	0.103	0.474
Water	1.096	0.011	0.021	0.029	0.036	0.044	0.002	0.007	0.029	0.105	0.501
Elect. Gen. - Coal	1.073	0.011	0.02	0.027	0.031	0.035	0.002	0.006	0.028	0.1	0.459
Elect. Gen. - Solar	1.069	0.01	0.02	0.027	0.031	0.034	0.002	0.006	0.028	0.099	0.454
Services	1.064	0.012	0.022	0.029	0.034	0.039	0.002	0.007	0.029	0.101	0.467
Fisheries	1.028	0.017	0.031	0.039	0.038	0.036	0.003	0.009	0.035	0.102	0.43
Elect. Gen. - Oil	0.973	0.013	0.024	0.032	0.036	0.041	0.002	0.007	0.029	0.096	0.444
Mining	0.918	0.009	0.017	0.023	0.026	0.029	0.001	0.006	0.024	0.085	0.385
Manufacturing	0.707	0.009	0.016	0.021	0.024	0.025	0.001	0.005	0.019	0.067	0.305
Petroleum	0.395	0.004	0.008	0.011	0.012	0.014	0.001	0.003	0.011	0.037	0.171
Chemicals	0.392	0.004	0.008	0.011	0.012	0.014	0.001	0.002	0.011	0.037	0.172

Similar to income, a K1 billion positive shock in final demand of construction commodities results in K0.03 billion, K0.12 billion and K0.42 billion in labour earnings for the low, medium and high skill markets respectively. On the whole, the high skill labour market dominates earnings for every increase in demand. This suggests that without deliberate (exogenous) efforts, increasing final demand would not lead to increased employment opportunities among the less educated workforce.

Table 7: Disaggregated Labour Effects (Units: K billion)

Commodity	GDP	Labour - Low	Labour - Medium	Labour - High
Elect. Gen. - Gas	1.178	0.025	0.049	0.326
Livestock	1.167	0.047	0.138	0.341
Elect. Distr.	1.135	0.023	0.033	0.403
Crop	1.131	0.024	0.055	0.24
Elect. Gen. - Hydro	1.127	0.017	0.028	0.249
Elect. Gen. - Other	1.121	0.025	0.05	0.326
Construction	1.111	0.028	0.117	0.42
Forestry	1.104	0.041	0.206	0.259
Elect. Gen. - Wind	1.101	0.02	0.042	0.281

Water	1.096	0.021	0.037	0.376
Elect. Gen. - Coal	1.073	0.021	0.038	0.26
Elect. Gen. - Solar	1.069	0.02	0.038	0.247
Services	1.064	0.028	0.046	0.303
Fisheries	1.028	0.029	0.127	0.255
Elect. Gen. - Oil	0.973	0.024	0.071	0.347
Mining	0.918	0.013	0.042	0.202
Manufacturing	0.707	0.017	0.035	0.191
Petroleum	0.395	0.009	0.018	0.103
Chemicals	0.392	0.009	0.016	0.11

Under the unconstrained multiplier model (results for which are in Tables 5-7), it was assumed that the supply side of the economy has sufficient resources to meet all changes on the demand side. This is not usually true as there could be competition for resources on the supply side. For example, expansion of the crop activities means less land is available for forestry activity. This unconstrained supply side assumption tends to overestimate the multiplier effect of a demand shock in the economy (Haggblad et al., 1991).

Therefore, Table 8 provides results showing the magnitude and uncertainty of the effects that constraining an activity (see Equation (5) above) would have on GDP, income, output and total demand respectively.

From the four tables, it can be seen that constraining the services activities has the largest impact on the economy. For instance, if final demand for all other commodities is increased by one unit (K1 billion) but the services activities are constrained, relative to unconstrained model, GDP, household income and output would reduce by 75% (with uncertainty at 0.454 standard deviation), 106% (0.682) and 55% (0.316) respectively. This highlights the critical role and strong linkages that services activities play in Zambia's economy. Thus, it would be important that barriers that could limit the growth of these services activities are reduced.

Among the energy sector projects, electricity production from hydro-power has the largest impacts and introduces the most uncertainty across the four macroeconomic indicators. This is an important finding because Zambia's electricity supply is hydro-power dominated and future electricity production from hydro-power is expected to be considerably impacted by the changing climate. This, therefore, suggests that diversifying from hydro would be critical to enhancing socioeconomic development in Zambia. This finding is in line with that of Carlino et al. (2023), who found that hydropower expansion would not be competitive in the long term along the Zambezi River Basin.

Table 8: The Effects of Activity Constraints

Activity	GDP		Income		Output		Total demand	
	Average Change	Std. Dev.						
Services	-0.745	0.454	-1.059	0.682	-0.545	0.316	-0.109	0.035

Mining	-0.127	0.231	-0.179	0.29	-0.099	0.186	-0.027	0.051
Construction	-0.124	0.221	-0.178	0.345	-0.094	0.099	-0.021	0.015
Manufacturing	-0.108	0.107	-0.152	0.154	-0.088	0.145	-0.021	0.046
Elect. Gen. - Hydro	-0.076	0.145	-0.105	0.217	-0.063	0.23	-0.014	0.047
Petroleum	-0.069	0.252	-0.098	0.36	-0.062	0.154	-0.014	0.053
Chemicals	-0.066	0.252	-0.094	0.361	-0.06	0.224	-0.013	0.035
Crop	-0.061	0.128	-0.092	0.174	-0.048	0.113	-0.012	0.028
Forestry	-0.061	0.191	-0.085	0.257	-0.046	0.15	-0.012	0.041
Livestock	-0.057	0.147	-0.082	0.198	-0.046	0.141	-0.011	0.028
Fisheries	-0.056	0.184	-0.079	0.257	-0.045	0.11	-0.009	0.031
Water	-0.055	0.208	-0.077	0.29	-0.042	0.142	-0.008	0.033
Elect. Distr.	-0.048	0.145	-0.068	0.204	-0.041	0.152	-0.008	0.024
Elect. Gen. - Coal	-0.04	0.152	-0.058	0.224	-0.033	0.127	-0.008	0.033
Elect. Gen. - Oil	-0.039	0.162	-0.054	0.223	-0.03	0.129	-0.008	0.034
Elect. Gen. - Solar	-0.036	0.153	-0.052	0.226	-0.029	0.126	-0.008	0.034
Elect. Gen. - Wind	-0.035	0.151	-0.05	0.22	-0.026	0.104	-0.008	0.022
Elect. Gen. - Other	-0.034	0.146	-0.048	0.21	-0.025	0.108	-0.008	0.033
Elect. Gen. - Gas	-0.032	0.14	-0.046	0.202	-0.025	0.108	-0.008	0.033

4.2 The macroeconomic implications of energy investments

Table 9 below summarises the unconstrained macroeconomic impacts of specific energy sector investments as given in Table 4 above (in Section 3 above). The average yearly capital investment from 2020 to 2050 is US\$977 million, US\$2,116 million and US\$1,272 million for the reference, centralised and decentralised scenarios respectively.² The results suggest that for every unit of investment in the energy sector, the centralised scenario offers better multiplier effects than both the reference and decentralised scenarios. It should be noted however that the difference of multiplier effects between scenarios is minimal across all the four macro-economic indicators (GDP, income, output and total demand). This is in part because over this period of time (on average) both the centralised and decentralised scenarios are dominated by solar and wind (centralised at 52%, and decentralised at 72%).

Table 9: Macroeconomic Impacts of Specific Energy Sector Capital Investments (USD 2019, Millions)

Variable	Reference	Centralised	Decentralised
Investment level (input)	977	2116	1272
GDP	1,087.4	2,347.8	1,393.0
Income	728.3	1,588.2	940.0

² See Nyambe-Mubanga et al. (2023) for the detailed description of these scenarios.

Output	1,822.1	4,151.6	2,479.3
Total Demand	2,598.2	5,884.2	3,520.2
GDP / Investment	1.113	1.110	1.095
Income / Investment	0.746	0.751	0.739
Output / Investment	1.866	1.962	1.950
Total Demand / Investment	2.660	2.781	2.768

This finding can also be inferred from Table 6 and 7 above. These tables show that Zambia's labour (factors) and income (households) have similar distributions across all energy technologies. Therefore, investing in a particular technology over another would not significantly change the behaviour of macro-economic indicators.

5. Concluding Remarks

A SAM, as a framework, provides for a consistent way to conduct macroeconomic analysis for a country or region, in a given year. This macroeconomic analysis can act as a critical input in assessing energy investments, climate action options and socioeconomic plans that a country might be considering, among others.

In this paper, we highlighted the key structural aspects of the Zambian economy as of 2019. Aspects such as economic activities that offer growth opportunities (under the unconstrained model) and economic activities which would act as bottlenecks of growth if a conducive environment is not created (under the constrained model) were outlined.

Our analysis of the impacts of growth through increased demand clearly demonstrated that different economic activities have varying effects on GDP, income, output and total demand. For instance, activities that contribute more to GDP may not always contribute significantly to household income and output. It is worth noting that the high skill labour market dominates earnings for every increase in demand, which suggests that without deliberate (exogenous) efforts, increasing demand in the economy would not lead to increased employment opportunities among the less educated workforce. Policies are needed that ensure that economic growth therefore can benefit all parts of the workforce and households, to meet the broader development objectives of the Zambian government. Furthermore, the analysis also shows that limiting activities in services, mining and construction sectors would have considerable negative impacts on the economy, particularly on GDP and income.

The analysis of specific energy sector investments on macroeconomic indicators shows that even though the total capital investment across scenarios are different, per capital investment unit effects are similar. This is somewhat expected because the technology investment profiles of the centralised and decentralised scenarios are similar, both dominated by solar and wind technology. Overall, we show that energy investments present strong effects on all the four macroeconomic indicators (GDP, income, output and total demand). Thus, investing in the energy sector should be encouraged whether it is focused on centralised or decentralised technologies.

This near-equivalence between scenarios in terms of macroeconomic outcomes might provide greater flexibility for policy makers to choose investment according to “secondary” considerations, such as ensuring investment benefits a broader spectrum of the workforce, provides more spatially equitable benefits across regions, and meets other energy sector objectives.

An additional insight concerns the relative higher importance of hydropower on the economy. Given the potential future impacts of climate on hydro potential, diversifying the electricity to end the dominance of hydro would be critical to enhancing socio-economic development in Zambia. This points policy into the same direction as Carlino et al. (2023); they predict that the declining cost of wind and solar power in the Zambezi River basin will make a large fraction of the current hydropower candidate installations economically uncompetitive over 2030-2050 anyway.

The value and importance of these research findings notwithstanding, we are of the view that further macroeconomic analysis needs to be conducted. The use of a CGE model on this SAM (or similar disaggregated SAMs) and investment profile data would add considerable value and enhance decision making. As mentioned in the earlier section, a SAM multiplier model is a static model, thus the use of a CGE model was better to capture the dynamics of systems development and also give a more comprehensive representation of the effects of the energy investments on the economy.

Author credit

The multiplier analysis presented in this paper was undertaken by Bernard Tembo. The paper was written by Bernard Tembo and Steve Pye. Earlier work to develop the SAM used in the paper was supported by Matthew Winning, Metin Piskin and Alvaro Calzadilla (UCL).

Acknowledgements

This work was funded by the Climate Compatible Growth programme of the UK government. The views expressed here do not necessarily reflect the UK government’s official policies. The authors would like to thank Mathias Weidinger (Oxford University) for his very helpful review of an earlier version of the paper.

Model / data Availability

The SAM used in this analysis can be found at <https://zenodo.org/records/10808457>

References

1. Aguiar, A., Chepeliev, M., Corong, E., McDougall, R., & van der Mensbrugge, D. (2019). The GTAP Data Base: Version 10. *Journal of Global Economic Analysis*, 4(1), 1-27. Retrieved from <https://www.jgea.org/ojs/index.php/jgea/article/view/77>
2. Breisinger, C., Thomas, M., and Thurlow, J. (2009). *Social Accounting Matrices and Multiplier Analysis: An introduction with exercises*. Food Security in Practice technical guide 5. Washington D.C.: International Food Policy Research Institute.
3. Carlino, A. et al. (2023). Declining cost of renewables and climate change curb the need for African hydropower expansion. *Science* Volume 381. DOI:10.1126/science.adf5848
4. Chikuba, Z., Syacumpi, M., and Thurlow, J. (2013). *A 2007 Social Accounting Matrix (SAM) for Zambia*. Lusaka, Zambia; and Washington, D.C.: Zambia Institute for Policy Analysis and Research; and International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI).
5. Cooper, R. and John, A. (2012). *Macroeconomics: Theory through Applications*, Publisher: Saylor Foundation
6. Garrett-Peltier, H. (2017). Green versus brown: Comparing the employment impacts of energy efficiency, renewable energy, and fossil fuels using an input-output model, *Economic Modelling*, Volume 61
7. GRZ (2006). *Vision 2030*. Technical report, GRZ, Lusaka.
8. GRZ (2016). *National Policy on Climate Change (NPCC)*. Government of the Republic of Zambia.
9. GRZ (2019). *National Energy Policy*. Lusaka: Government of the Republic of Zambia.
10. GRZ (2022). *Eighth National Development Plan (8NDP) 2022-2026*. Technical report, GRZ, Lusaka.
11. Haggblade, S., J. Hammer, and P. Hazell. (1991). Modeling agricultural growth multipliers. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics* 73 (2): 361–74.
12. Howells, M., Necibi, T., Laitner et al. (2021). *Integrated Input-Output and Systems Analysis Modelling: The Case of Tunisia*. Part 1 - Energy technology Input-Output multipliers, PREPRINT (Version 2) available at Research Square, <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-336989/v2>
13. Howells, M., Rogner, H., Strachan, N., et al. (2011). OSeMOSYS: The Open Source Energy Modeling System. *Energy Policy*, 39(10):5850–5870.
14. ILO. (2017). *How to measure and model social and employment outcomes of climate and sustainable development policies*. Geneva: International Labour Organisation.
15. Mainar-Causepe, A., Ferrari, E., and McDonald, S. (2018). *Social Accounting matrices: basic aspects and main steps for estimation*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.
16. Milani R, Caiado Couto L, Soria R, Szklo A, and Lucena AFP. (2020). Promoting social development in developing countries through solar thermal power plants. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Volume 246
17. Miller, R. E. and Blair, P. D. (2009). *Input-Output Analysis: Foundations and Extensions*. Cambridge University Press, second edition.
18. Nyambe-Mubanga et al. (2023). *Greening the Recovery in Zambia*. Technical report, UCL, London.
19. Pauw, K., Randriamamonjy, J., and Thurlow, J. (2022). *2021 Social Accounting Matrix for Zambia: A Nexus Project SAM*.
20. Pauw, K., Tembo, B., and Thurlow, J. (2021). *2019 Social Accounting Matrix for Zambia: A Nexus Project SAM*.

21. Peterson, S. (2003). CGE models and their application for climate policy analysis. Integrated Climate Models: An interdisciplinary assessment of climate impacts and policies. Trieste.
22. Pyatt, G., & Thorbecke, E. (1976). Planning Techniques for a Better Future. Geneva: International Labour Office.
23. Sigwele, H. (2007). The effects of international trade liberalization on food security and competitiveness in the agricultural sector of Botswana PHD Thesis. Pretoria: University of Pretoria.
24. Stone, R. (1947). Measurement of national income and the construction of social accounts . Geneva: United Nations.
25. Tembo, B. (2023). Zambia's Social Accounting Matrices: A comparative analysis (Draft)
26. Vasconcellos, H.A.S. and Caiado Couto, L. (2021). Estimation of socioeconomic impacts of wind power projects in Brazil's Northeast region using Interregional Input-Output Analysis, Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, Volume 149,
27. Winning, M., Piskin, M., Calzadilla, A, and Tembo, B. (2023). Note on Energy-extended Social Accounting Matrix (SAM) for Zambia
28. ZamStats (2022). 2010 Social Accounting Matrix (SAM) for Zambia. Lusaka, Zambia (Unpublished).
29. ZESCO, 2022. Annual Electricity Statistics (2009-2020).

Annexes

Annex 1: Name Convention of the Aggregated Variables

Table A1: SAM Aggregation Mapping

Description	SAM 2019 CCG	Name
Activities - Maize	amaiz	Crop
Activities - Rice	arice	Crop
Activities - Other cereals	aocer	Crop
Activities - Pulses	apuls	Crop
Activities - Oilseeds	aoils	Crop
Activities - Roots	aroot	Crop
Activities - Vegetables	avege	Crop
Activities - Sugarcane	asugr	Crop
Activities - Tobacco	atoba	Crop
Activities - Cotton and fibres	acott	Crop
Activities - Fruits and nuts	afroi	Crop
Activities - Coffee, tea and cocoa	acoff	Crop
Activities - Other crops	aocrp	Crop
Activities - Cattle and raw milk	acatt	Livestock
Activities - Poultry and eggs	apoul	Livestock
Activities - Other livestock	aoliv	Livestock
Activities - Forestry	afore	Forestry
Activities - Fisheries	afish	Fisheries
Activities - Mining	aCoal	Mining
Activities - Mining	aOil	Mining
Activities - Mining	aGas	Mining
Activities - Mining	aOmin	Mining
Activities - Processed foods	afood	Manufacturing
Activities - Beverage and tobacco	abeve	Manufacturing
Activities - Textiles, clothing and footwear	atext	Manufacturing
Activities - Wood and paper products	awood	Manufacturing
Activities - Chemicals and petroleum	aPetrol	Petroleum
Activities - Chemicals and petroleum	aChem	Chemicals
Activities - Non-metal minerals	anmet	Manufacturing
Activities - Metals and metal products	ametl	Mining
Activities - Machinery, equipment and vehicles	amach	Manufacturing
Activities - Other manufacturing	aoman	Manufacturing
Activities - Electricity, gas and steam	aEdist	Elect. Distr.
Activities - Electricity, gas and steam	aEnuc	Elect. Gen. - Nuclear
Activities - Electricity, gas and steam	aECoa	Elect. Gen. - Coal
Activities - Electricity, gas and steam	aWind	Elect. Gen. - Wind
Activities - Electricity, gas and steam	aEothe	Elect. Gen. - Other

Activities - Electricity, gas and steam	aEGas	Elect. Gen. - Gas
Activities - Electricity, gas and steam	aEHydro	Elect. Gen. - Hydro
Activities - Electricity, gas and steam	aEOil	Elect. Gen. - Oil
Activities - Electricity, gas and steam	aESolar	Elect. Gen. - Solar
Activities - Electricity, gas and steam	aGdist	Gas Distr.
Activities - Water supply and sewage	awatr	Water
Activities - Construction	acons	Construction
Activities - Wholesale and retail trade	atrad	Services
Activities - Transportation and storage	atran	Services
Activities - Accommodation and food services	ahotl	Services
Activities - Information and communication	acommm	Services
Activities - Finance and insurance	afsrv	Services
Activities - Real estate activities	areal	Services
Activities - Business services	absrv	Services
Activities - Public administration	apadm	Services
Activities - Education	aeduc	Services
Activities - Health and social work	aheal	Services
Activities - Other services	aosrv	Services
Commodities - Maize	cmaiz	Crop
Commodities - Rice	crice	Crop
Commodities - Other cereals	cocer	Crop
Commodities - Pulses	cpuls	Crop
Commodities - Oilseeds	coils	Crop
Commodities - Roots	croot	Crop
Commodities - Vegetables	cvege	Crop
Commodities - Sugarcane	csugr	Crop
Commodities - Tobacco	ctoba	Crop
Commodities - Cotton and fibres	ccott	Crop
Commodities - Fruits and nuts	cfru	Crop
Commodities - Coffee, tea and cocoa	ccoff	Crop
Commodities - Other crops	cocrp	Crop
Commodities - Cattle and raw milk	ccatt	Livestock
Commodities - Poultry and eggs	cpoul	Livestock
Commodities - Other livestock	coliv	Livestock
Commodities - Forestry	cfore	Forestry
Commodities - Fisheries	cfish	Fisheries
Commodities - Mining	cCoal	Mining
Commodities - Mining	cOil	Mining
Commodities - Mining	cGas	Mining
Commodities - Mining	cOmin	Mining
Commodities - Processed foods	cfood	Manufacturing
Commodities - Beverage and tobacco	cbeve	Manufacturing
Commodities - Textiles, clothing and footwear	ctext	Manufacturing

Commodities - Wood and paper products	cwood	Manufacturing
Commodities - Chemicals and petroleum	cPetrol	Petroleum
Commodities - Chemicals and petroleum	cChem	Chemicals
Commodities - Non-metal minerals	cnmet	Manufacturing
Commodities - Metals and metal products	cmetl	Mining
Commodities - Machinery, equipment and vehicles	cmach	Manufacturing
Commodities - Other manufacturing	coman	Manufacturing
Commodities - Electricity, gas and steam	cEdist	Elect. Distr.
Commodities - Electricity, gas and steam	cENuc	Elect. Gen. - Nuclear
Commodities - Electricity, gas and steam	cECoa	Elect. Gen. - Coal
Commodities - Electricity, gas and steam	cEWind	Elect. Gen. - Wind
Commodities - Electricity, gas and steam	cEOthe	Elect. Gen. - Other
Commodities - Electricity, gas and steam	cEGas	Elect. Gen. - Gas
Commodities - Electricity, gas and steam	cEHydro	Elect. Gen. - Hydro
Commodities - Electricity, gas and steam	cEOil	Elect. Gen. - Oil
Commodities - Electricity, gas and steam	cESolar	Elect. Gen. - Solar
Commodities - Electricity, gas and steam	cGdist	Gas Distr.
Commodities - Water supply and sewage	cwatr	Water
Commodities - Construction	ccons	Construction
Commodities - Wholesale and retail trade	ctrad	Services
Commodities - Transportation and storage	ctran	Services
Commodities - Accommodation and food services	chotl	Services
Commodities - Information and communication	ccomm	Services
Commodities - Finance and insurance	cfsrv	Services
Commodities - Real estate activities	creal	Services
Commodities - Business services	cbsrv	Services
Commodities - Public administration	cpadm	Services
Commodities - Education	ceduc	Services
Commodities - Health and social work	cheal	Services
Commodities - Other services	cosrv	Services
Transaction costs	trc	trc
Factors - Labor - Low (not finished primary schooling)	flab-n	Labour - Low
Factors - Labor - Medium (finished primary, but not secondary)	flab-p	Labour - Medium
Factors - Labor - High (finished secondary and/or tertiary schooling)	flab-s	Labour - High
Factors - Agricultural land	flnd	flnd
Factors - Capital	fcap	fcap
Enterprises	ent	ent
Households - Rural (quintile 1)	hhd-r1	hhd-r1
Households - Rural (quintile 2)	hhd-r2	hhd-r2
Households - Rural (quintile 3)	hhd-r3	hhd-r3
Households - Rural (quintile 4)	hhd-r4	hhd-r4
Households - Rural (quintile 5)	hhd-r5	hhd-r5

Households - Urban (quintile 1)	hhd-u1	hhd-u1
Households - Urban (quintile 2)	hhd-u2	hhd-u2
Households - Urban (quintile 3)	hhd-u3	hhd-u3
Households - Urban (quintile 4)	hhd-u4	hhd-u4
Households - Urban (quintile 5)	hhd-u5	hhd-u5
Government	gov	gov
Taxes - Direct (personal or corporate)	dtax	d_tax
Taxes - Exports (products)	etax	e_tax
Taxes - Imports (products)	mtax	m_tax
Taxes - Sales, excise and/or value-added (products)	stax	s_tax
Savings-investment	s-i	s_i
Differences - Change in stocks	dstk	dstk
RoW - Rest of world	row	row
Total	total	total

Annex 2: Extension of the Zambia’s 2019 Social Accounting Matrices

(Based on work by Matthew Winning, Metin Piskin, Alvaro Calzadilla, & Bernard Tembo)

The objective of this work was to create an economic database with detail on various energy and electricity options in order to be able to consider the economic impacts of green growth and energy transitions. The following document details the methodology undertaken as part of the TRAP-ZM project in adding detail on electricity and energy sectors to the Zambia 2019 SAM developed by IFRPI. It then provides information on how this dataset will potentially be used and extended in the future.

The work undertaken uses the SAM database constructed for Zambia by Pauw et al. (2021) as the starting point and splits three sectors - the ‘mining’ (mine), ‘chemicals and petroleum’ (chem), and ‘electricity, gas and steam’ (elec) activity and commodity sectors - into more detail to give a total of sixteen sectors.

The correspondence between the old and new sectors are shown in Table 1. The intention was to use remain entirely consistent with the original IFPRI SAM and split the three sectors using other data, therefore, it should be to simply aggregate the new sectors, created and detailed in this document, together to create the original SAM.

The main other data sources used to undertake the disaggregation are electricity generation statistics from Zesco Limited Power (ZESCO, 2022) and the Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP 10) database (Aguiar et al. 2019). The former provided us with the electricity generation by technology in 2019 for Zambia, the base year of the IFPRI SAM. The latter, the GTAP-Power database, provided us with a SAM for Zambia for 2014 which does have greater detail on the sectors of interest here. Therefore, it was possible to use the GTAP database to inform the cost structure in our disaggregation. For the sake of simplicity, we do not disaggregate between base load and peak electricity generating technologies and therefore when using GTAP-Power data these are aggregated together and considered as one (e.g., in GTAP-Power there are both baseload and peak electricity generation from gas and oil, these are combined for our database).

Table A2: Mapping of old sectors to new sectors

IFPRI original sector	Description	New sectors	Description
mine	Mining	coal	Mining of coal
		oil	Oil extraction
		gas	Extraction of gas
		Miner	All other mining including metals, minerals etc.
chem	Chemicals and petroleum	Petrol	Petroleum, coal products
		Chem	Chemical products
elec	Electricity, gas and water	Edist	Electricity transmission and distribution
		Enucl	Electricity from nuclear energy
		Ecoal	Electricity from coal power

	Ewind	Electricity from wind power
	Eothe	Electricity from other power sources
	Egas	Electricity from gas
	ehydro	Electricity from hydro power
	eoil	Electricity from oil
	esolar	Electricity from solar power
	gdist	Gas distribution and transmission

We also cross-checked the electricity data with the model outputs from the OSeMOSYS-Zambia modelling as part of TRAP-ZM. There are several electricity technologies which currently have no generation in national statistics and have no entries in GTAP 10 for 2014. Yet, according to OSeMOSYS results, many will potentially be utilised by Zambia's power sector in the future such as wind power. In order for these technologies to be considered using a macroeconomic model i.e., an Input Output (IO) or Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) analysis, then it is necessary to have them included in the initial database, in this instance the SAM. Therefore, the sectors which currently do not were all given extremely small outputs in the base year and have cost structure which will allow their output to grow in future time periods.

Using both GTAP sectoral shares for the mining and petroleum and chemicals sectors as well as Zesco data on electricity generation in 2019, the sectoral output for the new sectors were constructed as given in Tables A3 and A4 and Figure A1.

Table A3: Mining output split

Coal	2.743%
Oil	0.274%
Gas	0.001%
Omin	96.981%

Figure A1: Chemicals output split

Table A4: Electricity, gas and steam output split

Edist	21.508%
Enucl	0.000%
Ecoal	8.894%
Ewind	0.005%
Eothe	0.005%
egas	0.005%
ehydro	65.749%
eoil	3.179%
esolar	0.627%
gdist	0.000%

The mining sector predominantly consists of other non-fossil fuel mining with a small amount of coal mining and very little of gas and oil. The petroleum and chemicals sectors are not too far off being evenly split, while the electricity sector is dominated by hydro production with some amounts of coal and oil. The SAM was then constructed using these sectoral output shares to determine the total output of each sector.

Next, the cost structure was determined from the Zambian 2014 SAM in GTAP for the sectors which have non-zero output. The small sectors which do not at present exist, but were included due to OSeMOSYS results, required to take a cost structure from elsewhere as they did not exist in the Zambian 2014 SAM, therefore, a SAM for the European Union used for the cost structure of technologies such as solar and wind. However, all these cost structures could only be included in so far as they kept in with any entries in the original and therefore only i.e., if there was an input from food manufacturing to coal mining in GTAP, but not in the IFPRI SAM, then the entry in our extended SAM is simply zero. Manual adjustments were then required to make sure the SAM balanced properly and tried to capture logical transfers e.g., oil extraction is sold to the petroleum refinery sector.

Annex 3: Zambia's Social Accounting Matrices Comparative Analysis

(based on work undertaken by Bernard Tembo)

Introduction

The International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI) has developed two Social Accounting Matrices (SAM) in quick succession, with base years of 2019 (Pauw et al., 2021) and 2021 (Pauw et al., 2022). It is not clear what the main differences are between these two SAMs. Therefore, this comparative analysis highlights the key differences between the SAMs. This is important because the 2019 SAM has a base year (2019) which some analysts consider as representative to Zambia's economy pre-COVID-19 pandemic while the 2021 SAM has a base year during a period Zambia was still battling the COVID-19 pandemic. Thus, one could also think of this analysis as highlighting the structural changes that took place in the economy as a result of COVID-19 (as the long-term stable structure of the economy is as captured in the 2019 SAM).

Key Results

In this section, highlights of the two SAMs are given. The comparative discussion of these SAMs are deliberately kept light and thus the analysis only focuses on the structure of the economy (production and trade), tax revenue and household transactions (income and expenditure of households).

Macro-SAM for Zambia (millions of Kwacha)

A SAM captures "transactions and transfers between all economic agents in a system" (Miller and Blair, 2009, pg. 514). In Table A5 and A6, macro-SAMs are given with base years of 2019 and 2021 respectively. These macro-SAMs aggregates sectoral transactions, thus giving a good overview of the circular flows of both income and expenditure in an economy.

Table A5: 2019 Macro-SAM for Zambia

	act	com	fac	ent	hhd	gov	tax	s-i	dstk	row	tot
act	0	491,824	0	0	3,375	0	0	0	0	0	495,201
com	222,403	169,547	0	0	114,608	60,042	0	107,407	10,540	103,792	788,337
fac	272,799	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	610	273,408
ent	0	0	160,948	0	0	24,432	0	0	0	0	185,379
hhd	0	0	106,694	99,615	0	175	0	0	0	1,273	207,760
gov	0	0	0	13,156	2,550	0	49,056	0	0	3,470	68,231
tax	0	24,630	0	8,778	15,648	0	0	0	0	0	49,056
s-i	0	0	0	63,830	70,714	-20,074	0	0	0	3,476	117,947
dstk	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10,539	0	0	10,539
row	0	102,341	5,763	0	859	3,655	0	0	0	0	112,618
tot	495,201	788,337	273,408	185,379	207,760	68,231	49,056	117,947	10,539	112,618	

Table A6: 2021 Macro-SAM for Zambia

	act	com	fac	ent	hhd	gov	tax	s-i	dstk	row	tot
act	0	767,241	0	0	3,447	0	0	0	0	0	770,688
com	356,031	250,398	0	0	115,351	83,586	0	130,626	12,626	227,630	1,176,248
fac	414,657	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	195	414,853
ent	0	0	202,772	0	0	30,412	0	0	0	0	233,184
hhd	0	0	175,875	124,673	0	834	0	0	0	5,786	307,168
gov	0	0	0	16,969	1,813	0	40,280	0	0	5,897	64,959
tax	0	9,817	0	11,090	19,374	0	0	0	0	0	40,280
s-i	0	0	0	80,452	165,442	-51,400	0	0	0	-51,242	143,252
dstk	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12,626	0	0	12,626
row	0	148,792	36,206	0	1,742	1,526	0	0	0	0	188,266
tot	770,688	1,176,248	414,853	233,184	307,168	64,959	40,280	143,252	12,626	188,266	

Structure of production and trade in Zambia

Comparing 2019 to 2021, the total gross domestic product (GDP) at factor cost increased from K272,799 million to K414,657 million. Table A7 below shows the aggregated breakdown of GDP at factor cost. From the Table, it can be seen that the share of the Services category shrank the most while the share of the Industry category increased the most. Actually, of the three categories, only the Industry category increased, as the Agricultural category also reduced.

Table A7: Structure (in %) of GDP at factor cost in Zambia

Group	2019 SAM	2021 SAM
Agriculture	3.47	3.03
Industry	35.47	47.76
Services	61.07	49.21

The structure of production and trade of Zambia's economy is given in Tables A8-A11. These Tables also highlight the impact that trade has on the overall economy.

From Table A8 it can be seen that Industry dominates Zambia's exports, this dominance increased during the COVID-19 pandemic (in 2021). Compared to before the pandemic, the share of Services reduced considerably, from 12.8% to 4.1%. Of the three categories, the Services is the only one which experienced a reduction. As could be expected, relative to total production, the share of exports of the Services category also reduced, with considerable increase in the Agriculture and Industry category, as can be seen in Table A10.

Similarly, from Table A9 it can be seen that Industry dominates Zambia's imports. Interestingly, during the COVID-19 pandemic (in 2021), Zambia imports relatively more Services and Agricultural goods and services than before the pandemic. However, during the pandemic, Zambia's economy (across all the three categories) became more dependent on imports in order to meet local demand, this can be seen in Table A11.

Table A8: Export Structure (in %) of Trade in Zambia

Group	2019 SAM	2021 SAM
Agriculture	2.23	2.39
Industry	84.95	93.48
Services	12.82	4.12

Table A9: Import Structure (in %) of Trade in Zambia

Group	2019 SAM	2021 SAM
Agriculture	0.89	0.92
Industry	82.76	80.30
Services	16.35	18.78

Table A10: Export/Output Structure (in %) of Trade in Zambia

Group	2019 SAM	2021 SAM
Agriculture	13.08	23.71
Industry	41.65	55.38
Services	5.07	2.61

Table A11: Import/Local Demand Structure (in %) of Trade in Zambia

Group	2019 SAM	2021 SAM
Agriculture	3.69	4.75
Industry	26.74	28.06
Services	6.48	7.58

Sources of Tax Revenue in Zambia

From Table A12, it is shown that the structure of tax revenue in Zambia is noticeably different. Whereas it was estimated that direct and indirect taxes in 2019 were almost 50%-50%, the sources of tax revenue in 2021 were dominated by direct taxes, which accounted for at least 75%. Such variance in structure has different tax administration and policy implications.

Table A12: Structure of tax revenue (%) in Zambia

SAM	Direct	Indirect		
	Personal & Corporate	Exports	Imports	Sales/VAT
2019 SAM	49.79	0.23	6.92	43.05
2021 SAM	75.63	0.02	3.53	20.82

Sources of Income for Households in Zambia

Table A13 highlights the distinction between rural and urban households in terms of their main sources of income. From the Table, it shows that income from labour factor accounts for at least 61% of the income of rural households. However, in urban areas, the sources of income are varied. This implies that urban households are more resilient to shocks in the labour markets, shocks such as changes of tax rates in the labour related earnings. Noticeable also is the role of land factor, both SAMs highlight the role that this factor plays in rural households' income. This structure is consistent in both SAMs.

Table A13: Structure of household income (%) in Zambia

Region	Quintile	SAM	Labour			Land	Capital			Transfer		
			Total Lab.	Low	Medium	High	Land	Total Cap.	Capital	Ent	Govt	World
Rural	Q 1	2019 SAM	64.94	11.96	35.54	17.44	9.44	24.26	4.41	19.85	0.03	1.33
Rural	Q 1	2021 SAM	71.38	10.90	41.75	18.73	8.58	16.55	3.75	12.80	0.10	3.38
Rural	Q 2	2019 SAM	62.73	9.13	32.05	21.55	10.20	25.39	5.43	19.96	0.05	1.63
Rural	Q 2	2021 SAM	69.27	8.55	38.62	22.10	9.74	16.84	4.79	12.05	0.12	4.03
Rural	Q 3	2019 SAM	61.73	5.72	27.24	28.77	9.66	27.53	6.05	21.47	0.06	1.01
Rural	Q 3	2021 SAM	69.21	5.50	35.54	28.18	9.92	18.05	5.56	12.50	0.17	2.64
Rural	Q 4	2019 SAM	63.64	3.87	16.76	43.00	6.63	28.80	5.05	23.75	0.09	0.84
Rural	Q 4	2021 SAM	71.60	3.76	23.93	43.91	7.16	18.72	4.67	14.05	0.27	2.25
Rural	Q 5	2019 SAM	71.38	3.10	4.76	63.53	2.99	25.15	3.55	21.60	0.09	0.39
Rural	Q 5	2021 SAM	77.11	3.27	6.74	67.10	3.36	18.12	3.44	14.68	0.23	1.17
Urban	Q 1	2019 SAM	61.22	6.12	40.07	15.03	1.48	35.62	0.56	35.06	0	1.67
Urban	Q 1	2021 SAM	67.26	5.58	45.68	16.00	1.25	26.57	0.51	26.05	0.27	4.66
Urban	Q 2	2019 SAM	54.24	9.28	24.60	20.36	1.60	42.32	0.65	41.67	0.25	1.60
Urban	Q 2	2021 SAM	59.92	8.66	28.98	22.28	1.42	33.19	0.53	32.66	0.75	4.72
Urban	Q 3	2019 SAM	50.44	3.79	21.36	25.30	0.64	47.80	0.39	47.41	0.12	0.99
Urban	Q 3	2021 SAM	57.61	3.63	25.83	28.15	0.59	38.38	0.33	38.05	0.38	3.04
Urban	Q 4	2019 SAM	42.50	3.04	8.29	31.17	0.29	56.37	0.24	56.13	0.11	0.72
Urban	Q 4	2021 SAM	49.43	3.03	10.57	35.82	0.29	47.60	0.21	47.39	0.36	2.33
Urban	Q 5	2019 SAM	44.87	1.93	3.09	39.84	0.14	54.47	0.25	54.22	0.08	0.45
Urban	Q 5	2021 SAM	50.78	1.96	4.06	44.76	0.14	47.33	0.24	47.09	0.26	1.49

Household Expenditure in Zambia

When household expenditure is considered, poorer households spend most of their income on consumption, whereas richer households are more likely to save a significant portion of their income. This can be inferred from Table 10 below. As noted under the sub-Section looking at sources of household income, this expenditure behaviour means that richer households have a more robust safety network in an event of a shock. Also highlighted in the Table is the variance in household spending between 2019 and 2021 SAM base years.

Table A14: Structure of households expenditure (%) in Zambia

Quintile	SAM	Consumption	Taxes	Savings	RoW
Q 1	2019 SAM	81.10	0.44	18.46	0
Q 1	2021 SAM	64.66	0.43	34.91	0
Q 2	2019 SAM	78.09	1.32	20.59	0
Q 2	2021 SAM	60.69	1.23	38.08	0.00
Q 3	2019 SAM	70.52	3.01	26.44	0.03
Q 3	2021 SAM	51.92	2.64	45.40	0.04
Q 4	2019 SAM	61.15	5.83	32.96	0.06
Q 4	2021 SAM	42.00	4.92	52.99	0.10
Q 5	2019 SAM	53.72	9.14	36.54	0.59
Q 5	2021 SAM	35.08	7.58	56.53	0.81

Concluding remarks

From this brief analysis, it can be concluded that the two SAMs are different in all the three aspects (structure of production and trade, taxation and household characteristics). These differences have considerable implications on policy and administrative actions. Therefore, care must be taken when choosing one SAM over another as the starting structure of the economy will be different. Compared to the 2019 SAM, it is presumed that the 2021 SAM has effects of the COVID-19 pandemic baked into it.